

Online Supplementary Materials

Psychological Resilience and Adverse Mental Health Issues in the Thai Population During the Coronavirus Disease 2019 Pandemic

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Supplementary Online Content

Figure S1 Flow Diagram for Study Participations

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Figure S1 Flow Diagram for Study Participations

Abbreviation: HOME-COVID-19, The Health Outcomes and Mental Health Care Evaluation Survey Research Group—Coronavirus Disease 2019.